

FINAL REPORT

September 10th 2021

About

This document reports the results of the citizen-science pilot project “Water Sentinels” (initially entitled “Keepers of the sea”) financed by the EU within the ACTION project (Horizon 2020 R&I program under grant agreement number 824603).

This pilot was promoted by Ocean Alive, and involved two scientific partners: Centre for Energy and Research (CINEA, Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal) / Setúbal School of Technology (Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal) and MARE Marine and Environmental Research Centre (University of Lisbon).

Figure 1: Water sentinels pilot launch banners (with promoter, ACTION and partners logos)

According to the pilot project plan (available at our shared nextcloud folder, version 11032021, in “Keepers of the sea > contract > uploads), this report will provide information to the ACTION consortium on:

1. results and conclusions;
2. eligible costs documentation;
3. deliverables (milestones 1-3);
4. interim updates.

1. Results and conclusions

Water sentinels pilot allowed us to achieve important results and to learn valuable lessons for future projects, especially citizen-science (CS) projects. In this section we will discuss what we consider to be the main results, taking into account the original

project plan and comparing to what was achieved. We will also discuss about the major challenges, and how the pilot overcome those challenges.

Water sentinels original aim was to foster citizen science on fishing communities, in order to promote water quality and tackle water pollution events at Sado estuary. We proposed to reach this aim by:

- a) empowering people from the community to be leaders of CS for water quality (through training and participation in the scientific process);
- b) collecting data on water pollution events (current and historical), to fill gaps and provide valuable information to researchers, managers and decision-makers;
- c) producing tools to enhance engagement and community participation in detecting water pollution issues.

From our project plan (6 months ago):

With this pilot, the community will be capacitated, engaged in water quality data collection and signal major water pollution events. Researchers and managers will have new baseline data to assess. In the near future we envision a better collaboration between community and researchers.

In six months we envision a better collaboration between the fishing community and researchers to promote water quality on the estuary. With 20 people involved in the project and a part of them trained on experimental procedures for water quality assessment, the awareness about pollution issues will be raised and people will be prepared to repeat the collaboration whenever is necessary. Also, baseline data will be gathered, which can be crossed with other projects data and may support policy and management decisions. Although we cannot guarantee that major pollution events will occur during the ACTION six month pilot span, we will at least establish a baseline dataset to compare with when these events happen in the future.

Today we believe our vision was accomplished. Water sentinels pilot engaged the community in water quality assessment and prepared the participants to better detect water pollution events. The project created two datasets, one available in open access and one only available for researchers. These data contributes to the knowledge about the water quality at Sado estuary. Participants are now prepared to repeat the collaboration, if needed, and researchers want to include them in a longer project (2021-2023), currently being held by a scientific partner (IPS). Although data collected could not support the detection of a major pollution event during the 6 months' time-frame of this pilot, it gives information about highly probable locations for this to happen. It also reinforces the need to continue monitoring, and contributed to improve the pesticides analysis method in the laboratory.

RESULTS

>> Participants engaged

- 4 citizens were trained and participated in the current data water sampling design and collection; 5 were considered on original plan.
- 21 participants answered the historical data/perception questionnaires; 20 were considered in the original plan.

The water quality topic was highly engaging for most participants, who were happy to participate on the project, and provide their contribution by sharing knowledge and local experience. However, since water pollution is a sensitive issue in such small communities, the protection of participants data privacy became mandatory. This privacy issues affected the engagement of people outside the previously established network, and prevented any focus group or group events to be held.

4 participants were engaged in the project, and trained for water sample collection until June. The training for water sampling was started with a 5th participant, but it was not finished with success. The participant initially agreed to be trained, received the sampling kit and was taught how to use it, but did not collect any water samples. Due to this, we are not including this participant as a result in this report.

>> Data created

Two datasets were created by this pilot:

- Dataset 1: resulting from the water samples analysis (made available in open access, with the exception of exploratory pesticides analysis);
- Dataset 2: resulting from the historical data / perceptions data from questionnaires (not made publically available; it will be shared with researchers upon a non-disclosure agreement).

About Dataset 1:

This open access dataset presents data and metadata for water quality assessment on 17 water samples collected at Sado estuary by citizens during the 6-month pilot. The samples were analyzed by students and researchers at Setúbal School of Technology (Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal). It is already published in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/record/5498267>) and available through the website page.

The data collected by citizens at the field was location (GPS coordinates), temperature and water transparency (using the secchi disc method). In the laboratory researchers evaluated pH, salinity, conductivity, and concentration of ammonia, nitrate, phosphate, suspended solids (SST) and organic matter (SOM and DOM).

Figure 2: Sampling points at Sado estuary (sample 6 is not shown).

We made available 17 out of 18 sample results for this parameters, since one of the sampling points could raise legal questions due to location (possible private property). The sampling points showed a good geographical coverage of the estuary and were selected in collaboration with the trained citizen's participation and scientific partners validation. By involving participants in the process, we integrated their local knowledge in the choice, and their motivation to assess specific pollution problems. Water samples were collected by participants (autonomously and assisted by pilot's team) from May 4th to July 28th 2021.

About the results of the analysis by scientific partner, the conclusions are the following. Overall, most samples showed relatively low values of organic matter and nutrients. Only three samples have slightly higher values both of organic matter and nutrients, two located on the south bank and one on the north bank, corresponding to samples collected very close to land (less dilution effect). The analyzed parameters generally indicate good water quality, although there may be many others that may affect the estuary and need to be monitored.

An exploratory pesticides analysis was also made in 5 out of 18 water samples, screening for herbicides occurrence (penoxsulam, atrazine, propanil, cyhalofop-buthyl). Since this method is still being tested at this laboratory, data is confidential

and conclusions are made with caution. Most samples revealed herbicide values lower than detection limit (mainly for cyhalofop-buthyl), and below quantification limit. One sample, however, showed a high concentration for penoxsulam, which was detected and quantified. These results will not be made public, since they need further research and validation.

About Dataset 2:

Dataset 2 was created using the answers to the historical data / perceptions questionnaire. 21 participants were interviewed in-person, one-to-one or in small groups, by the pilot's team in June - July. This dataset was not uploaded in the nextcloud folder since the full dataset will be kept confidential, as it was accorded with partners and ACTION team. The privacy of these data will avoid conflicts with stakeholders or misinterpretation of the data collected by third parties, which could otherwise compromise project sustainability.

The geographical data collected with this method will be shared only with scientific partners, upon a non-disclosure agreement (in preparation). An exploratory analysis was made, which led to this decision.

The data from perceptions, however, was treated and results will be public; preliminary results on perceptions were shared in workshop for stakeholders and will be part of the layman's report.

Participants profile was mostly men (71%), over 41 years (86%), with an education level between the primary and middle school. All participants had a strong connection with the estuary, where they live and work (>90%, activities mainly related to fishing, shellfish gatherers and aquaculture). 76% of the participants belong to the community located north at the estuary (Setúbal).

Because they revealed a strong link to the estuary, they also showed a high self-perception about their knowledge on the quality of the water (20/21 classify as well to very well) and ability to recognize water pollution events (18/21 classify as well to very well).

Regarding their perception about the temporal evolution of the water quality in the estuary, from the past to nowadays, their answers showed a positive evolution trend, of improvement. Today they classify the water quality as good to very good (mean=4.2 in a scale from 1 to 5, in which 1 is very bad and 5 is very good), and before they classify as bad (mean=2 in the same scale). Most participants are older than 41 years, so this classification refers to at least 3-4 decades ago.

Participants pointed out to have observed signals of water pollution at the estuary in multiple occasions (not only in the past, but today still). The signs of pollution most indicated were foams and changes in water colour or transparency, followed by oils and dead fish and shellfish. Other signs mentioned were marine litter, hot water and dust (originated from air deposition near air pollution sources).

The problems they indicate as more important to be addressed nowadays are the industrial and agricultural effluents, followed by domestic sewage and marine litter.

Most participants believe the water quality can still improve in the estuary (90% indicates “yes” to “yes, a lot”, mean=4.5 in a scale 1-5). The solutions they suggest more frequently are to increase the inspection activities and to bring awareness to the people/entities causing the problems. Other solutions mentioned are changes on the legislation, and to increase collaboration between those who live/work on the estuary, researchers and decision-makers. In a minor extent, some participants suggest about the education role, to report of the problems on media and to increase investment in water treatment infrastructures.

When questioned about “who would benefit the most on water quality improvement” the results were clear: 20 out of 21 selected “everyone”.

The results of this perceptions seem to be shared with what both researchers and managers have been assessing in the estuary in the last decades, which was highlighted for them during the workshop for stakeholders.

>> Impact assessment

The impact assessment plan evolved during the pilot, and was carefully analyzed together with ACTION team. Both ex-ante and ex-post questionnaires for participants were co-created and translated to Portuguese. However, only ex-post data on impact assessment on participants was collected from participants with a stronger connection with the project (n=4).

A motivation assessment for participants was also prepared. The questionnaire was answered by 4 participants.

Regarding the impact assessment questionnaire for CS managers, we already started filling it but were still not able to finish all the answers to the questionnaire. We expect to fulfill this task and send it to ACTION team next week (until September 15th).

>> Data quality

The analysis and assurance of data quality was also made as expected, in collaboration with ACTION team. After answering an ex-ante data quality questionnaire for CS managers (May 12th), we made the analysis and assurance of the data quality using ACTION template (May 26th). With this analysis we defined data quality indicators (DQIs) and actions to be implemented in order to improve data quality. This document is available at nextcloud shared folder (Keepers of the sea > deliverables > Water sentinels_Data quality assurance (...)). Most DQI goals were achieved, except for the number of samples collected, which was slightly below the original number proposed (18 instead of 20).

>> Data management

A data management plan was established earlier in the pilot, including contributions and reviews from ACTION mentor and scientific partners. This plan evolved during the pilot, since adjustments were necessary to the privacy of the data generated. Three versions of DMP were delivered during the pilot. The final version is available in the shared folder.

>> Communication and materials developed

Communication plan:

A communication plan was developed in the beginning of the project (April 7th). This plan allowed us to define goals of communication, to define and rank target audiences, and to define tools to reach them. Although not all scheduled activities of the plan were made according to original plan, due to adjustments on the tasks schedule and privacy issues, we consider the goals of communication were achieved. 5 posts on social media were made, in 3 social media networks. The reach was higher on facebook posts (where the community is bigger).

Table 1: Publications of water sentinels pilot on Ocean Alive social media channels

Date	Content	Facebook			Instagram			Linkedin		
		Reach	Interaction	Share	Reach	Interaction	Share	Reach	Interaction	Share
10/09	Film	to be assessed								
2/07	Data collection	3264	120	10	982	51	5	172	8	0
28/05	Website Action	1036	52	4	1069	78	3	189	6	0
5/05	Citizens training	2068	98	15	1253	88	2	282	10	0
22/03	Pilot's launch	3880	235	47	1537	194	18	688	29	1

The pilot launch was made not only in Ocean Alive communication channels, but also by scientific partners media channels: in the news section of their websites (e.g. https://www.ips.pt/ips_si/noticias_geral.ver_noticia?P_NR=7931 , <https://www.mare-centre.pt/pt/lancado-projeto-sentinelas-da-agua>), internal newsletters and social media.

At September 10th the video was be made available in youtube and shared in social media channels. We will not be able to include the reach of this deliverable in this report, but we consider this content to be appealing to the public and expect it will have a good reach and interactions from audience. After the project we expect to create more 2 posts, to share the stakeholder's workshop held, and to share the website page where all project contents will be available.

Film/short documentary:

The pilot's film is already available on youtube
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F3W0AmixCSU>)

The film started to be prepared earlier in the project, since we believed it would be the best tool to engage people and spread awareness on the topic, while contributing to give a leadership role to the citizen-scientists who participated in the project. The first movie script considered using their images and stories as an inspiring example to be replicated for the audience. Legal documents to allow this participation according to the RGPD were developed, presented and explained to them in-person. However, during the pilot it was decided to maintain their identity private, to avoid conflicts in the community which could compromise their participation. A second script was developed with a different storyline, aiming to involve a more diverse figures (age, gender) and landscapes (rural, urban). This version presented a more holistic approach to the water quality issues. We are pleased with the final result, which we believe to gather important features:

- a) it is inspirational and diverse, appealing to a broad audience;
- b) it contains the information and results of the pilot, but it is not simply a "project film" which sustainability could be compromised with the pilot's end: because it also tells a story about water quality and how we are all linked to it, it will be an excellent tool keep discussing this issue in the future, for diverse publics/events;
- c) it uses simple and clear language (PT) and has captions available in English (on youtube);
- d) it included other people of the community in the footages (and also pilot's participants in backstage), maximizing the reach of the pilot with our target public; the film production was an engagement tool for itself.

Website page:

The website page was made available in September 8th, both Portuguese (<https://www.ocean-alive.org/sentinelas-da-agua>) and English versions (<https://www.ocean-alive.org/en/water-sentinels>).

This webpage contains all project information and links. Only the upload of community guide / layman's report was not possible yet (people are informed to be available soon), since a final version (revised) is still not available (see below more information).

Layman's report and community guide for water quality assessment:

We were not able to deliver a final version of these deliverables until September 10th. A preliminary version is available in nextcloud folder (Keepers of the sea > deliverables > community guide_laymans report_preliminary). Final versions will be provided to ACTION until September 15th.

>> Stakeholders engagement

One workshop for stakeholders was held online in September 8th. The workshop program was divided in 3 sections:

1. Presentation of water sentinels project (about the project and preliminary results), by project team (including scientific partners and mentor);
2. Presentation about the connection between water quality and seagrass health, by Ocean Alive;
3. Presentation about stakeholders' compromises to water quality, by participants.

The invitation to be part of this workshop was endorsed to >30 recipients (public administration, municipalities, industries, aquacultures). They were informed about this pilot activities and were invited to participate.

One of the aims of the workshop was to challenge this group of public and private entities to share their compromises (and future vision and targets) to the water quality at Sado estuary.

20 participants (representing 9 stakeholders, 2 research centers and 1 NGO (organizers)) attended this workshop. Participants included national entities responsible for water quality monitoring (ARH/APA, IPMA), for nature conservation (ICNF), municipalities (Setúbal) companies related with water regulation and wastewater treatment (AIA, Simarsul) and industries (Lisnave, Parmalat). One other important stakeholder (port authorities) could not be present, but manifested their will to know the results and engage in the follow-up activities (APSS). Slides developed by the participants are available at nextcloud folder (Keepers of the sea > deliverables > workshop sentinelas (...); in Portuguese).

For the workshop follow-up, Ocean Alive proposed that this event could be the first step on establishing a network of local stakeholders on this topic; participants were asked to provide a permit to add their contact to a participants list if they wish to be part. Also, Ocean Alive suggested specific actions who could be made to engaged everyone in the near future: for e.g. to organize an annual major cleanup in Sado estuary in September/October, beginning in 2022.

Once local government elections will be held in the end of the month, the water quality topic was also led by Ocean Alive to one of the local candidates hearing session. When asked what the municipality should be concerned in the near future, Ocean Alive representative (Raquel Gaspar) raised the water quality issue and the need to address it. The candidate proposed that a scientific conference on this topic should be held in Setúbal in the next years.

HIGHLIGHTS OF PILOT'S IMPACT

From the pilot's promoter perspective:

The pilot allowed our organization to:

- strengthen connection with the community and re-establish in-person scientific activities after a low activity gap due to pandemic;
- raise awareness on a topic (water quality) which is central to accomplish our mission: to protect and restore seagrass meadows by reducing threats to their health and providing them the best conditions for recover;
- enhance collaboration between citizens and scientists, raise public awareness and advocate for improvements with stakeholders;
- grow our citizen-science pilot and overcome challenges in a network of a diverse group of mentors, pilots and trainers who helped us to achieve this results;
- learn about data management, data protection and data quality in a citizen-science project;
- be part of a network of citizen-science pilots, learn and share with other European experiences in this field.

From the citizen's perspective:

For the 4 citizens involved in both water sampling design/collection and historical data and perception assessment (questionnaires), we highlight three results emerged from this pilot:

- a) the pilot's activities raised their knowledge on the water quality topic, brought more awareness about its importance, and about the scientific process;
- b) by reinforcing their ability to detect pollution events and their link to the scientific community it developed more self-confidence in their skills;
- c) because the project activities happened after a long period when most activities had been suspended due to the covid pandemic, it meant not only a reinforcement of their individual skills, but also a "return" to a closer collaboration with the promoter organization and activity for promoting seagrass health.

The next step for this participants will be to present them the water samples analysis results, the materials developed and discuss future steps towards a better water quality in Sado estuary.

Regarding the participants who only participated in the historical data/perceptions data collection (17), the project allowed them to share their local knowledge about the past and current pollution events, their perception about the problems, but also their vision and solutions. Although their link with the project activity was short, there were who participants kept reporting to the team what they considered to pollution signs occurring at the estuary, which they observed after being interviewed.

From the scientist's perspective:

This pilot was important for them, since all data, learning and stakeholders network will be integrated in a more extensive project (2021-2023), coordinated by scientific partner "IPS" (GI4Sado Developing an integrated management plan as a tool to support Sado estuary governance).

The scientific team manifested their will to maintain the connection with the pilot's participants, to assess their availability to keep contributing to this issue participating in GI4Sado. Also, the use of this pilot water samples for pesticides screening helped to improve the specific methodology at this laboratory, and resulted in preliminary data which will be confirmed in the future.

Coastnet platform is not able, at the moment, to make available online the data from partners regarding physico-chemical parameters of water samples (the platform layers are being prepared to comply with FAIR principles, which will happen soon). However, open access dataset was shared with the geoportal coordinator and will be integrated in this platform when possible.

Regarding historical data and perceptions collected with questionnaires, the geographical data was not made available for the public, but it will be shared in the future with the project researchers through a non-disclosure agreement (in preparation). These data will also be important for future water quality assessments, to fill knowledge gaps and contribute to the pollution events detection in the future.

From the stakeholder's perspective:

Stakeholders were involved in a later stage of the project, but were still able to benefit from the activities. The pilot's workshop for stakeholders was important to present them the project, the major findings and conclusions, but also to allow for an opportunity to reflect and share about their entities/companies compromises to improve water quality at Sado estuary.

CHALLENGES

>> Need to assure participants' privacy

The ACTION support in data privacy was crucial to raise our awareness on the importance of assuring protection of personal data, inform participants and openly discuss related issues with participants. At first, this raise some concerns in our participants, since they have low literacy and they become uncomfortable when there is the need to make contracts and sign documents. This discussion led to the decision of maintaining participant's privacy, for their protection and engagement. This decision brought changes in our original plan and strategy (e.g. film, see below), adding a layer of difficulty in completing the tasks. From that moment on all tasks needed to be made in-person with each participant separately.

This challenge was discussed with ACTION team and other pilot's in the interims. We believe this challenge was overcome successfully, and we learn important lessons on data privacy, to avoid problems later in the projects.

>> Participants low literacy (digital, languages)

Since our target public has low digital literacy, all training methods, questionnaires (for historical data/perceptions, impact assessment, motivation) were made in person and mediated by the Ocean Alive team. Also, each question needed to be explained and frequently "put in another words" carefully, almost at an individual level, to be sure the message was clear and data being collected was as it was supposed to be. All materials had to be developed with that perspective in mind. An extra effort was needed from our team, but we are confident it worked out.

This is also one of the reasons we are not able to deliver the final layman's report and guide for the community at September 10th, since we need to assure it is, on one hand, scientifically accurate, and on the other hand, accessible to our target public.

>> Water pollution is sensitive data – restrictions to make data available

Since water pollution is a sensitive topic which can bring negative consequences to stakeholders and communities, we had to carefully assess which data we could make available in open access, to not compromise the project aims, but also our longer connection with participants and stakeholders at the estuary.

We had to adjust our initial data management plan to have restrictions to a part of the data collected (namely pesticides exploratory analysis and geographical data related to pollution locations).

All decisions were made after presented to ACTION team and in close connection with scientific partners.

>> Pilot's time frame and uncertainty regarding sanitary measures evolution (covid pandemic)

The time schedule for water sentinels pilot was March 15th to September 10th.

When the project began Portugal was emerging from a lockdown situation, with sanitary measures being updated every 15 days. This risk was discussed and take into account in the original project plan, but this still had an impact, to a certain degree, on the project execution flow. Fortunately, the situation regarding sanitary measures evolved positively during the pilot, but we had to adjust our plans almost monthly, and make an effort to fulfill every task involving in-person meeting every time this was seen as necessary.

One of the consequences of this situation (and time-frame) was the delay in delivering the workshop. In July we concluded we would not be able to have

engagement from the stakeholders, since after the lockdown people were focused on delivering their tasks and go on vacation to rest, and did not show to be open to participate in something which would add more to their efforts. In August most people is on vacation too, so the only moment available within the pilot's time frame to best reach our objectives with this deliverable was near the end of the project (2nd week of September). We saw this moment as crucial for the project sustainability, as an opportunity to set the basis for future collaboration regarding this topic, but the time-frame was tight and not perfect (some people are returning to work or still in vacation this time of the year). The solution for the success of this workshop was to try to reach the target entities/persons by diverse channels (email, phone), with a high effort in engagement and communication.

>> Demanding plans (due to pilot short term)

ACTION provided much more than funding to our project and NGO. The participation in ACTION accelerator was crucial to achieve this results and to prepare our small team to successfully address challenges in the future on topics we were not comfortable about before this pilot.

However, by participating in this accelerator program we also assumed many compromises we did not fully understand at first. To learn some topics from scratch (e.g. data management plans, data quality indicators, impact and motivation assessment, RGPD, interims) demanded an effort and consumed more time than initially previewed when we prepared the project plan. This is mainly challenging due to the pilot short term. This challenge was only possible to overcome due to the close mentorship and all ACTION team help provided to our team.

Figure 3: Movie plan, showing a young woman sampling water © João Esteves/Ranna

2. Eligible costs documentation

Eligible costs documentation, comprising ACTION cost statement and invoices for costs over 1000€, can be found in the shared nextcloud folder (“Keepers of the sea” > Deliverables > Final report).

The executed costs were all close to the previewed initially on the budget. Hence, we considered the pilot had a good financial execution.

Costs with “staff salaries” exceeded in 386,77€ the original budget, which is attributed to a small change in Raquel Gaspar salary occurred during the pilot, and the need to allocate a higher time share to Sílvia Tavares (from 50% originally, to 70% in the first trimester and to 60% during the second trimester). The update on time share resulted from the need to actively engage in all accelerator tasks, to prepare, adjust and deliver all the pilots plans (data management, communication, data quality, impact assessment, legal issues regarding citizens informed participation), especially in the beginning of the pilot, while we were also starting to engage the participants and the researchers.

Costs with “travel” exceeded in 118,44€ the original budget. This change is attributed to the specific need of this project to carefully engage participant’s in-person, due to low literacy and low digital skills challenges. The first approach by pilot’s team also triggered the need to assure participants privacy, in order to avoid any conflicts within the communities. This issue prevented any group activities, hence more travel was needed than initially expected.

Costs with “other goods and services” were lower than the ones considered in the original budget (less 324,70€). This difference is mainly due to: a) we were able to find sampling kits material similar but cheaper than the original budget (secchi discs, thermometers); b) we obtained a discount on the online meetings service for non-profits; c) website page designer was not able to provide all services initially previewed and d) community guide prints were not produced. Materials and services not previewed in the original budget were also needed to deliver the pilot. Most materials were included in the citizen-scientists sampling kits, and had to be adjusted to their specific needs. Also, there was a cost with other services provider needed to complement the website page design and to give to support the stakeholder’s workshop, which are detailed in the cost statement document.

Regarding the costs with “subcontracting”, a small change occurred between the original budget for consultancy and the executed cost, with a positive budget of 103.07€.

Overall, the difference between the total cost requested in the original budget (19.973,25€) and the one executed in the project (2095.81€) is -122.56€ (< 1% total budget available for pilots).

Figure 4: Movie plan, showing water sampling process by citizens © João Esteves/Ranna

3. Deliverables (milestones 1-3)

>> Milestone 1:

- 2 data collection protocols
 - Data collection protocol for current data can be found in nextcloud folder (“Keepers of the sea > Deliverables > Experimental protocol for water sampling_water sentinels_14May21”)
 - Questionnaire for historical data collection is available in nextcloud folder (“Keepers of the sea > Deliverables > Sentinelas da agua_questionário para obtenção de dados históricos”)
- Data management plan
 - Available at “Keepers of the sea > Deliverables > DMP Keepers of the sea_OA_10Sep21” (last version).
- First training and data collection
 - First training and data collection was finished with success in May 3rd. Results for this sample are included in the first dataset, presented here, and were reported in the interim 2 meeting slides.
- Impact assessment plan
 - An impact assessment plan was determined with ACTION team support; we planned to collect data in two moments (ex-ante in May/June and ex-post in July/August) and questionnaires were prepared, translated to Portuguese and adapted to our target public, in two versions (online and printable);

- The ex-ante and ex-post questionnaires are available at “Keepers of the sea > Deliverables > water sentinels_ex-ante questionnaire (...) AND water sentinels ex-post questionnaire;
- A motivation survey was also prepared for the participants, to be implemented during the pilot. It is available in the same folder: “Keepers of the sea > deliverables > ex-ante_survey about motivation-v2-pt”.
- Communication plan
- Available at “Keepers of the sea > Deliverables > communication plan_final_7Apr21”

>> Milestone 2:

- 2 datasets regarding water pollution events are created
- 1 dataset (current data) was created in June and updated at the final of the project (available at nextcloud shared folder Keepers of the sea > deliverables > water sentinels_analytical determinations(...)) and published in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/5498267>, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5498267
- 1 dataset (historical data) was be created with data from questionnaire answers, but will not be made available.
- 5 fisherwomen are trained for water sampling and water quality reporting
- 4 project participants were engaged, fully trained and participated in project tasks; 1 participant started training, but did not developed sampling activities.

>> Milestone 3:

- 1 webpage on OA website

Available at www.ocean-alive.org/sentinelas-da-agua (portuguese version) and at www.ocean-alive.org/en/water-sentinels (english version)

- 1 online workshop on water quality for stakeholders
The online workshop was held at September 8th 2021. Slides for the workshop presentation (from pilot’s team and participants) are available at nextcloud shared folder (Keeper of the sea > deliverables > workshop sentinelas (...))
- 2 datasets (realtime and historic)
See milestone 2
- 1 short documentary video
Available on <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F3W0AmixCSU> and shared on our website and social media channels.

- 1 community guide for water quality assessment; 10 prints of the guide + 1 layman's report

A preliminary version of the community guide is available at nextcloud folder (Keepers of the sea > deliverables > community guide_laymans report_preliminary). We expect to validate this deliverable with partners next week, and deliver a final version to ACTION until September 15th.

4. Interim updates

All slides from the interim updates can be found in the shared nextcloud folder ("Keepers of the sea > Interim updates"). It includes slides from interims 1 to 4 (May 5th, April 6th, June 2nd and June 30th). The pilot's team participated in all interim meetings, presenting their progress with the pilot, discussing challenges to this progress and brainstorming solutions with ACTION team and other pilots.

Figure 5: Movie plan about our link to the water © João Esteves/Ranna